

The HuT

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2

Deliverable D6.5

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation,
T6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy

AUTHORS

Ilaria Bonetti (ICONS), Eylul Aksekili (ICONS),
Erica Moresco (ICONS), Francesca Galloni (ICONS)

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Project Coordinator	Michele Calvello UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO mcalvello@unisa.it
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- * PU = Public
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3. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D6.5) presents the updated **Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan** of The HuT project at M37. It outlines the progress achieved in engaging stakeholders, sharing project knowledge, and preparing for the post-project use, replication, and sustainability of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

Compared to the initial strategy (D6.1), this updated plan reinforces the integration between **dissemination and exploitation** to ensure that project outputs are not only communicated and disseminated, but also effectively adopted by their intended users – local authorities, civil protection agencies, researchers, industry actors, educators, policymakers, non-profit organisations/NGOs, as well as industry actors such as corporations, engineering and technology companies, and financial or insurance institutions.

Key advances include:

Communication & Dissemination (C&D)

- The C&D strategy has been updated and refined to better align with the project's progress, stakeholder engagement, and exploitation pathways. The integration of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) into communication planning ensures that all formats from editorial outputs to audiovisual content are tailored to support uptake and impact.
- The HuT expanded its range of dissemination formats, including factsheets, newsletters, press and news releases, video interviews, social media campaigns, and journalistic articles, all designed to reach diverse audiences with accessible, engaging, and targeted content.
- These efforts have also contributed to building a growing community around the project, fostering stakeholder loyalty and continuous interaction.
- Through consistent storytelling, cross-platform visibility, and collaboration with sister projects and EU initiatives, The HuT has been effectively positioned as a reference project in the fields of disaster risk reduction, resilience, and science–society interaction.
- The overall strategy has evolved from raising awareness to driving impact, shifting focus from visibility to the uptake and transferability of results, preparing the ground for the final phase of exploitation and replication activities.

Exploitation – Main Achievements

- 24 KERs and sub-KERs have been identified, characterised, and grouped into six thematic clusters to facilitate integrated exploitation:
 - Local and International DRR Forums
 - Local Data Portals
 - Education and Capacity Building
 - Scientific Modelling, Monitoring and Technological Innovation
 - Operational and Policy Protocols
 - Financial Instruments for Risk and Climate Management

- For each KER, IP (intellectual Property) ownership, and IPR (Intellectual Property Right) management, TRL (Technology Readiness Level), accessibility, potential users, and exploitation strategies were defined.
- The exploitation strategies designed for The HuT's combined institutional uptake (e.g. Local DRR Forums integrated into municipal governance), technological exploitation and service models (e.g. Local Data Portals, IoT monitoring systems, Dynamic Exposure Modelling services), scientific and academic valorisation (methodologies, models, publications), and education and capacity-building actions (DRR Academy, serious games, school materials). Results with higher TRL are being prepared for operational deployment or commercial pathways in collaboration with municipalities, SMEs and insurance partners, while research-oriented KERs will continue to be exploited through open access, scientific networks, and future projects. Most exploitation plans propose a mixed sustainability model, where institutional commitment, open-access tools/data, and potential revenue-generating services coexist to ensure continuity beyond the project. The progressive development of exploitation roadmaps (planned in the final project year) will further define ownership, governance, funding mechanisms, and replication strategies for each KER or cluster.

What comes next

In the final project phase (M38–M48), exploitation efforts will shift towards:

- Developing concrete exploitation roadmaps, including business/replication models and post-project governance;
- Exploring funding schemes and partnerships for long-term sustainability (EU programmes, national funds, industry);
- Finalising IPR agreements, particularly for jointly developed technological solutions;
- Delivering **D6.4 Final Exploitation Plan**.

4. Introduction

Achieving The HuT's goal of employing innovative, community-centered solutions to prevent and manage extreme climate events, is supported and amplified by the implementation of a robust and integrated Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy.

This strategy ensures that The HuT's outcomes deliver tangible and long-lasting impacts across its target audiences, fostering the uptake of a comprehensive set of trans-disciplinary risk management tools and approaches that can be adopted and adapted throughout Europe.

One of the main objectives of this deliverable is to update and align the CDE strategy, initially defined in D6.1, with the project's progress up to M36. The CDE activities are designed to operate in synergy, ensuring a coordinated and consistent rollout that amplifies visibility, engagement, and impact. The integrated approach is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1: Integrated CDE approach.

This deliverable reflects the advances achieved since the initial CDE plan, incorporating insights from the continuous monitoring of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and outcomes from the project's progress in demonstration sites and thematic activities. The deliverable establishes the basis for creating targeted, exploitation-oriented dissemination materials and defines a roadmap for strategic outreach during the project's final phase.

Month 36 represents a key milestone to consolidate achievements, refine the CDE coordination mechanisms, and plan activities that will encourage stakeholder engagement and foster post-project uptake of The Hut's disaster risk management (DRM) solutions.

It is important to highlight that D6.5 serves as an update rather than a replacement of D6.1, which presents the preliminary CDE framework and remains the core reference document for partners regarding communication and dissemination procedures, responsibilities, and internal workflows. The CDE strategy will continue to evolve through an iterative process, adapting to project advancements and stakeholder needs. The forthcoming deliverables under WP6 include:

- D6.4: Consolidation of the Exploitation plan the Final Report (M48), outlining the exploitation strategy and post-project sustainability for The Hut's KERs.
- D6.6: Outreach and engagement activities v2
- D6.7: Networking activities v2.

4.1. Integrated approach to Communication Dissemination, and Exploitation

An integrated approach to CDE is essential to ensure the maximum impact, visibility, and uptake of research outcomes both during and beyond the project's lifetime. Through coherent coordination between CDE activities, The Hut aims to enhance awareness, share knowledge effectively, and enable the practical use of its results to support the prevention and management of extreme climate events.

The figure below (Figure 2) provides a visual representation of this integrated methodology and its evolution from M6 to M36. It outlines the main methodological steps, illustrates how they are interconnected, and shows how synergies between activities are developed and strengthened over time, together with their corresponding implementation timeline.

Figure 2: Integrated Methodology Evaluation.

4.2. Update of CDE Activities

Building on the preliminary work carried out up to M6, CDE activities have been fully integrated to ensure coherence across the project's outreach and impact actions.

The table below (Table 1) provides an overview of the CDE activities, summarising progress achieved so far and laying the groundwork for the next phase of implementation. The impact and effectiveness of this integrated strategy are continuously monitored and assessed through a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS which provides ongoing feedback to optimise, adapt, and strengthen CDE activities across the various phases of the project. The initial methodology and monitoring approach were defined in Deliverable D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, and have been further refined and implemented throughout the lifetime of the project.

Table 1: Overview of CDE activities.

	Timing	Status	Update	Deliverables
	M2	✓	Visual identity (logo, brandbook with rules, templates)	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
COMMUNICATION	M1 – M5	✓	Social media channels opened – LinkedIn, YouTube and X	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M6	✓	Website with Demo site pages in local language + partners' area	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M6	✓	Communication kit (video , leaflet, roll-up)	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M1- M48	↻	Editorial content production (Press, News, Event Releases)	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	M1- M48	↻	Monitoring	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	M1- M48	↻	Project animation and promotion via Social Media Channels and Project website	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	DISSEMINATION	M1-M48	↻	Networking Activities
M17-48		↻	Production of the Factsheets	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
M6- M48		↻	Scientific Publications	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
M38- M48		✗	Policy Briefs	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2

EXPLOITATION	Identification of KERs			
	M1- M6	✓	Identification and preliminary characterization of 18 KERs, based on the initial analysis of the Grant Agreement	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M6-M38	↻	Identification of 24 KERs and Sub-KERs, characterization, prioritization, and clustering, based on collaborative workshops, interview, and verification with partners.	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	M38- M48	✗	Final development of exploitation roadmaps and replication pathways for all the KERs identified	D6.4 – Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan
	IPR Management			
	M1- M6	✓	Mapping of IP ownership for each initial KER. Identification of foreground/background IP and confidentiality status.	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M6-M38	↻	Update and consolidation of IPR elements for all 24 KERs. Inclusion of IP protection measures (copyright, open-source licence, proprietary, trade secrets), access policies (open / restricted / internal). Identification of KERs requiring joint ownership or licensing agreements.	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	M38- M48	✗	Drafting formal IP agreements (e.g. Joint Ownership Agreements, licences, data-sharing agreements) if required. Support to partners in defining legal frameworks for service provision or commercial exploitation.	D6.4 – Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan
	Exploitation Strategies			
	M1- M6	✓	Initial identification of exploitation pillars and intended users of 18 KERs, detailing the main pathways for future uptake, replication and sustainability of The Hut's results.	D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results
	M6-M38	↻	Detailed exploitation strategies for each KER and sub-KER, structured into 6 thematic clusters to support joint exploitation (forums, data portals, capacity building, modelling & tech innovation, protocols, financial instruments).	D6.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2
	M38- M48	✗	Full exploitation roadmaps and business and/or governance models if relevant. Definition of replication strategies across DEMs and EU regions. Identification of funding schemes.	D6.4 – Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan

4.3. Structure of the document

Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The identification of the project's most relevant scientific innovations, technologies, and findings with strong potential for post-project uptake represents the first step in The Hut's integrated CDE approach. These results are classified as KERs or sub-KERs, depending on their scope, level of maturity, and relation to other project outputs. In addition to their scientific value, each KER is assessed in terms of feasibility, relevance, and expected socio-economic impact.

Progress and outcomes related to this activity are presented in Chapter 4.

Exploitation Strategy Development

Once KERs and sub-KERs have been clearly defined, specific exploitation strategies are designed to determine the most effective ways to leverage these results beyond the project's lifetime, ensuring their sustainability and long-term impact.

This process also involves considerations of Intellectual Property (IP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) to establish ownership, usage rights, and protection measures for the project's key outcomes.

The detailed definition of these exploitation strategies is reported in Chapter 4.

Oriented Dissemination Strategy

An integrated approach starts from the analysis of KERs and stakeholders to help re-orient a coherent and effective dissemination strategy. Indeed, an effective dissemination strategy implies choosing tailored channels, formats, and products to reach the right stakeholders. The current deliverable considers the KERs analysis and stakeholder consolidation as support to re-orient the dissemination strategy and target the formats correctly.

The dissemination formats span from scientific publications to policy briefs and info-packs.

Communication Activities

Integrating the KERs and stakeholder analysis helps drive the communication activities as well. This contributes to highlighting the value of KERs to a wide range of stakeholders. All communication materials are carefully customized depending on the channel used and, consequently, the target audience they will probably reach. The communication formats include press and news releases, journalistic articles, presentation videos, social media video clips and campaigns.

5. Update of The Hut's KERs and Exploitation Strategies

5.1. Methodology & Process

The exploitation methodology adopted in The Hut provides a structured framework guiding how results are identified, assessed, and leveraged for long-term impact (up to and beyond four years after the project ends). This methodology is implemented through an adaptive process that evolves in parallel with The Hut's technical and scientific progress, ensuring that outcomes generate value beyond the project's lifetime. Building on the insights gathered in D6.1 (M6), this process has advanced through several key phases: 1) the characterisation of KERs, the identification of new sub-KERs, prioritisation based on innovation potential, 2) the assessment of IP and IPR aspects, and 3) the co-definition of tailored exploitation strategies with the partners involved.

Figure 3: Exploitation Methodology.

Progress has been achieved through a combination of collaborative input collection and dedicated exploitation workshops held during the project's General Assemblies. This interactive and participatory approach has ensured continuous partner engagement and the progressive refinement of the exploitation framework.

The main steps of the process include:

- **First Exploitation Webinar (M25, online):** ICONS introduced the key elements of the exploitation process, including the concept of KERs, IP and IPR measures, accessibility, and exploitation pathways, while providing initial training to partners. During the webinar the Library of KERs was presented and shared. The Library of KERs is a living document consolidating all relevant information, continuously updated to monitor and refine project results.

- **First Input Collection (M25–M26):** Partners contributed to the Library of KERs. Each partner was invited to provide detailed information on their results with exploitation potential, marking the first collective effort to structure leverageable results emerging from the project.
- **First Exploitation Workshop (M26, General Assembly in Switzerland):** Partners worked collaboratively to map target users and define the value proposition of each KER, while discussing the key elements to consider in making their results as exploitable as possible.
- **Feedback Analysis (M26–M27):** ICONS reviewed the collected inputs to identify missing information or areas requiring further clarification, which informed the planning of the next exploitation activities.
- **Second Exploitation Workshop (M36, General Assembly in Hamburg):** This workshop focused on refining the characterisation of KERs and further developing exploitation strategies tailored to each partner. Particular attention was given to KER1 – Local DRR Nexus Forum and KER2 – Local Data Portals for each pilot site.
- **Feedback Analysis (M36–M37):** The completed templates and workshop outcomes were analysed to detect gaps, refine exploitation strategies, and identify the next steps to ensure effective post-project uptake of The Hut’s results.

5.2. KERs, IPR and Exploitation Strategies

Over the course of the HuT project, partners produce a wide range KERs — from digital platforms and early warning technologies to educational resources, scientific methodologies, policy recommendations, and insurance prototypes. These outputs reflect the complexity DRM, which requires an integrated approach across governance, data, technology, social awareness, and financial mechanisms.

To make these results easier to understand, transfer, and exploit beyond the project, they have been organised into thematic clusters. Each cluster brings together KERs that share a common purpose in the DRR cycle — whether it is community participation, data integration, scientific innovation, capacity-building, operational protocols, or financial resilience.

This structured approach allows us to:

- Highlight connections between results developed in different Work Packages and Demonstration Sites;
- Identify who can use each result (e.g. municipalities, schools, researchers, civil protection agencies, insurance actors);
- Clarify how results can be transferred, replicated or scaled to other territories or future projects.

In total, around **24 KERs and sub-KERs** have been identified. They vary in nature and include:

- **Digital tools and platforms** (e.g. Local Data Portals, Early Warning System prototypes, dynamic exposure services);
- **Scientific methodologies and models** (for multi-risk monitoring, fire prevention, heatwaves, exposure modelling);
- **Educational materials and training programmes** (Multihazard DRR Academy, school toolkits, serious games);

- **Governance mechanisms** (Local and International DRR Nexus Forums);
- **Operational and policy protocols** (EWS applications, inclusive communication guidelines);
- **Financial instruments** (climate-informed insurance products, risk transfer reviews).

These results cover all phases of the disaster risk management cycle — from prevention and preparedness to monitoring, early warning, response planning, recovery, and financing. To reflect this diversity, six clusters have been defined (Table 2).

Table 2: Clusters of KERs.

Cluster	Results
Cluster 1- Local and International DRR Nexus Forum	KER 1.1- Local DDR Nexus Forum-Amalfi
Cluster 2- Local Data Portals	KER 2.1- Local Data Portal- Amalfi KER2.2: Database of Pluvial Flood Events in Vilnius City Sub-KER2.2 a- Database of Precipitation (IDF Curves) for Vilnius Sub-KER2.2 b- Analysis of Precipitation Impact in Vilnius City Pilot Areas KER 2.3- Local Data Portal- Canton of Bern KER 2.4- Local Data Portal, Val d’Aran
Cluster 3- Education and Capacity Building	KER3.1- Multihazard DRR Academy KER3.2- Educational Materials for High School Pupils KER3.3- Serious Games for Cascading and Compound Impacts KER 3.4- Educational materials on DDR solutions KER 3.5- Educational materials on practices and strategies to react and adapt to urban pluvial floodings KER3.6- Educational material ("Fact sheet Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) curves in a climate change context")
Cluster 4- Scientific Modelling, Monitoring, and Technological Innovation	KER4.1-Innovative Nexus Monitoring KER4.2-Enhanced Monitoring Network (Val d’Aran) KER4.3- Prototype of Early Warning System KER4.4- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Software KER4.5- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Service KER4.6- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Data KER4.7- Methodology for the development of fire-prevention strategies KER4.8- Knowledge Advancements in Designing Fire Prevention Options KER4.9- Review of the Criteria for Heatwave Definition and Analysis of Past Heatwaves in the Valencia Region KER4.10- Methodology for the Analysis of Heatwaves and Urban Heat Island Effects

Cluster 5- Operational and Policy Protocols for Multi-Risk Management	KER5.1- Protocols for Early Warning System (EWS) Application KER5.2- Policy Recommendations and Briefs on Inclusive Risk Communication
Cluster 6- Financial Instruments for climate and risk management	Results within this cluster are not displaced, given the public nature of this deliverable

5.2.1. Local and International DRR Nexus Forum

This cluster brings together the Local DRR Nexus Forums and the International DRR Nexus Forum — complementary mechanisms designed to strengthen risk governance, cross-sector dialogue, and participatory decision-making in disaster risk reduction (DRR).

At the **local scale**, each Forum serves as a multi-stakeholder governance platform that connects different actors, such as municipalities, civil protection authorities, researchers, utilities, NGOs, Non-profit organisations, and communities to co-produce DRR strategies and operational decisions.

At the **international level**, the I-DRRnF extends this approach by fostering transnational exchange among scientists, practitioners, and policymakers, enhancing the transferability of knowledge and the scalability of DRR solutions.

Table 3: Cluster 1- KERs for Local and International DRR Nexus Forums.

KER 1.1- Local DRR Nexus Forum-Amalfi		
The Amalfi Forum focuses on hydro-meteorological and hydrogeological risk management in the coastal area. It involves the Municipality of Amalfi, Civil Protection, local utilities, NGOs, and academia, meeting regularly to discuss prevention measures and early warning procedures. The Forum operates through in-person meetings and an online workspace within the Local Data Portal (KER 2.1).	IP Owner: UNISA and municipality of Amalfi Accessibility: Open to relevant stakeholders; documentation and data are shared through the Local Data Portal	Exploitation Strategy: Designed for institutional exploitation, the Forum will continue after the project ends under the municipality's coordination. No dedicated budget is required; sustainability relies on staff time and stakeholder engagement, supported by periodic thematic initiatives managed by UNISA as part of its own activities.
KER 1.2- Local DRR Nexus Forum-Vilnius		
The Vilnius Forum targets urban flood and precipitation-related risks, involving municipality departments, utilities, insurers, civil protection, academia, and NGOs. It supports the co-production of the city's Climate Adaptation Strategy and uses a data-driven format, combining	Owner: Municipality of Vilnius and Vilnius University Accessibility: Open to forum members and local actors; reports available	Exploitation Strategy: The Forum is institutionally exploited as part of Vilnius' adaptation planning framework. Sustainability is ensured through university support and municipal integration, though continuity may depend on political stability.

<p>focused meetings and an online platform integrated with the Local Data Portal (KER 2).</p>	<p>through Vilnius University.</p>	
<p>KER1.3- Local DRR nexus Forum- Bern Canton</p>		
<p>The Bern Forum addresses forest and slope-risk governance in protection forests, involving forest managers, NGOs, cantonal authorities, hazard experts, and private stakeholders. It functions as a policy dialogue platform where research results are translated into actionable management recommendations.</p>	<p>Owner: Canton of Bern and UNIGE Accessibility: Restricted to institutional participants; results disseminated through reports and publications.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: The Forum will be integrated into cantonal DRR and forest management practices, sustained by local authorities and SEFRI funding. The key to sustainability is maintaining stakeholder participation and policy relevance.</p>
<p>KER1.4- International DRR nexus Forum (I-DRRnF)</p>		
<p>The International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) is a structured, multi-stakeholder platform that connects researchers, practitioners, and policymakers across Europe for knowledge exchange and co-development of disaster risk reduction (DRR) strategies. It fosters dialogue between Demonstrators and external experts to identify transferable practices, enablers, and barriers in multi-hazard management and risk governance. Each edition combines expert presentations and interactive sessions. The first Forum (Valencia, 2023) focused on stakeholder engagement and co-creation, while the second (Gerzensee, 2024) explored multi-hazard early warning systems (MHEWS) and nature-based solutions (NbS). Outcomes include policy insights, comparative analyses, and published deliverables.</p>	<p>Owner: UNIGE; UNISA Accessibility: Open format; deliverables and reports publicly available through project repositories.</p>	<p>The Forum model is designed for institutional and scientific exploitation, promoting exchange among researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Future exploitation pathways include: a) organisation of new editions in future EU or international projects, b) integration into international DRR frameworks (UNDRR, EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network), c) contribution to training programmes and academic dissemination. Sustainability depends on dedicated project or institutional funding for coordination and facilitation activities.</p>

5.2.2. Local data portals

The Local Data Portals are digital platforms that collect, visualise, and share data from IoT sensors, meteorological networks, and remote-sensing sources to support evidence-based decision-making in each Demonstration Site. They act as the data backbone of the Local DRR Nexus Forums (KER 1), enabling real-time monitoring, knowledge exchange, and coordination among stakeholders.

Each portal is tailored to local risks while following a common structure to ensure replicability and long-term usability. Most will remain operational beyond the project through local authority ownership and partner support, ensuring open access to non-sensitive data and institutional continuity.

Table 4: Cluster 2 - KERs for Local Data Portals.

KER 2.1 – Local Data Portal- Amalfi		
<p>Web-based platform integrating IoT monitoring sensors, meteorological datasets, and thematic maps to support hydro-meteorological and hydrogeological risk management in the Amalfi Coast DEM.</p> <p>It acts as the data backbone for the Amalfi Local DRR Forum (KER 1.1), providing real-time dashboards, maps, and decision logs.</p>	<p>Owner: Municipality of Amalfi and UNISA.</p> <p>Accessibility: Public web domain with open access to non-sensitive data; restricted access for specific layers (e.g. sensor data).</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: To be maintained jointly by the Municipality and UNISA after the project.</p> <p>Sustainability ensured through institutional integration (civil protection and planning activities).</p> <p>Updates managed by UNISA staff as part of ongoing academic and technical work.</p>
KER2.2- Database of Pluvial Flood Events in Vilnius City		
<p>A database of pluvial (rainwater) flood events in Vilnius compiled from the past 10 years, including event locations, timing, causes, and related meteorological data.</p> <p>The dataset identifies urban flood “hotspots” and documents how rainfall intensity and drainage system performance have evolved.</p> <p>It supports urban-resilience assessment, evaluation of storm-water infrastructure, and awareness-raising among municipal and national stakeholders.</p>	<p>IP Owner: Vilnius University (VU) with contribution from CMCC.</p> <p>Accessibility: Open/public; freely accessible for scientific, educational, and policy use.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: Used for scientific research and policy support, the database informs municipal planning and flood-risk mitigation.</p> <p>It will be maintained by VU for ongoing analysis and shared with public authorities to monitor infrastructure upgrades and identify priority zones for nature-based solutions.</p>
Sub-KER2.2 a- Database of Precipitation (IDF Curves) for Vilnius		
<p>A set of Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) curves developed for historical and projected climate periods.</p> <p>They provide quantitative insights into precipitation recurrence and intensity trends, enabling planners and engineers to design and adapt stormwater and drainage systems under changing climate conditions.</p>	<p>IP Owner: CMCC (with VU contribution).</p> <p>Accessibility: Open/public data product and methodological report.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: Supports urban-planning authorities, civil engineers, and researchers by supplying reliable rainfall design data.</p> <p>CMCC will update curves when new simulations are available, ensuring continuity and relevance.</p> <p>Serves as a standard reference</p>

		for future urban-climate and flood-risk projects. Agreements between CMCC and VU will be explored to enable CMCC to further exploit the results by offering consultancy services and applying the methodology in other contexts.
Sub-KER2.2 b- Analysis of Precipitation Impact in Vilnius City Pilot Areas		
A hydrological catchment-based analysis assessing the response of Vilnius's drainage systems to varying rainfall events. It evaluates whether existing rain-collection systems are adequate under current and projected climate conditions, providing a diagnostic baseline for urban-planning improvements.	IP Owner: CMCC and VU (joint). Accessibility: Open/public technical report and underlying data shared through academic channels.	Exploitation Strategy: The analysis guides decision-makers on infrastructure adequacy and climate-adaptation needs. Findings will feed into municipal planning discussions and serve as a template for replication in other cities facing similar challenges. Sustainability ensured through academic dissemination and inclusion in future climate-service projects.
KER 2.3 – Local Data Portal- Canton of Bern		
Data platform aggregating meteorological and hydrological information (e.g. TIS distometers, Fluvio weather sensors, MeteoGmbH datasets) in the Zulg River catchment. Supports local authorities in monitoring slope and forest-related hazards, linked to the Bern Nexus Forum (KER 1.2).	IP Owner: Meteo GmbH (with UNIGE and Canton of Bern support). Accessibility: Restricted to institutional partners; results disseminated through reports and dashboards.	Exploitation Strategy: Integrated into cantonal risk management workflows. Long-term sustainability secured through Canton of Bern's operational systems and collaboration with local data providers.
KER 2.4 – Local Data Portal, Val d'Aran		
It provides access to datasets, dashboards, maps, and decision-support tools related to multi-hazard risks in the area. The portal currently offers data visualisation and multi-hazard spatial representation of warnings, updated daily, enabling evidence-based decision-making and knowledge sharing among stakeholders. Developed and maintained by UPC	IP Owner: UPC and ARANTEC Accessibility: Online access via ARANTEC's infrastructure.	Exploitation Strategy: The portal will be maintained and operated by ARANTEC beyond the project, to transfer ownership or partnership to a local authority for long-term sustainability. Its exploitation pathway combines institutional use (by local civil protection services and municipalities) and commercial potential, leveraging

<p>and ARANTEC, the system builds on The HuT’s integrated DRR architecture and can be replicated across regions.</p>		<p>ARANTEC’s expertise in IoT and data-driven DRR tools. UPC will continue to support the scientific development and integration of multi-hazard visualisation features. The platform’s modular design enables replication and scaling in other mountainous or transboundary regions exposed to similar risks.</p>
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5.2.3. Education and Capacity Building

This cluster brings together results focused on training, awareness raising, and knowledge transfer to strengthen multi-hazard disaster risk reduction (DRR) capacities across different audiences — from young students to early-career researchers and practitioners.

These results aim to promote risk literacy, encourage interdisciplinary collaboration, and bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and societal preparedness. By combining open-access educational resources, participatory learning methods, and replicable training formats, this cluster contributes to building a culture of prevention and resilience at both local and European levels.

Table 5: Cluster 3 - KERs on Education and Capacity Building.

KER3.1- Multihazard DRR Academy		
<p>The Multihazard DRR Academy is a cross-disciplinary program for early-career researchers and practitioners. It delivers in-person sessions combining scientific, operational, and governance perspectives. Each edition gathers around 40 participants, encouraging collaboration across sectors and European regions. Training materials are shared online, ensuring broad access and reuse.</p>	<p>IP Owner: UNISA (training materials and format). Accessibility: learning material, freely reusable by future projects and organisations.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: The DRR Academy format will be replicated through future EU or national projects, supported by local organising committees. Each new organiser owns the material of their edition, ensuring adaptability. Sustainability relies on network-based cooperation and continued project-based funding rather than institutional embedding.</p>
KER3.2- Educational Materials for High School Pupils		
<p>An educational toolkit (presentation module + serious board game) focused on meteorological risks, climate change, and early warning systems, designed for high schools in the Campania region.</p>	<p>IP Owner: UNISA. Accessibility: Open access, hosted on Zenodo for free use and adaptation.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: The educational materials are primarily intended for schools, teachers, and public institutions in the Campania region, but they can also be easily adopted in</p>

<p>It complements the Serious Game, offering structured lessons and activities for civic education.</p>		<p>other European contexts through translation and adaptation to local curricula. The toolkit is designed for long-term use, with future updates and versions managed through the Zenodo repository, and it holds the potential to be integrated into broader EU education and awareness programmes focused on climate resilience and risk management.</p>
<p>KER3.3 Serious Games for Cascading and Compound Impacts</p>		
<p>A multi-version, multi-language serious board game that teaches risk perception, prevention, and management in single and multi-hazard scenarios (e.g. landslides, extreme weather). It encourages interactive and cooperative learning.</p>	<p>Owners: UNISA, CMCC, GFZ Accessibility: Open access (Zenodo)</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: Freely downloadable for educational use. Future exploitation may include print-on-demand or co-branded educational editions with publishers. Dissemination through scientific and educational events.</p>
<p>KER 3.4 Educational materials on DDR solutions</p>		
<p>This result consists of the dissemination of the THuT educational materials and DRR tools through the GNDR Community Platform, which connects more than 2,000 members across 132 countries. The materials include case studies, resilience stories, toolkits, and guidance on early warnings and innovative technologies. The platform acts as a knowledge hub for transferring and contextualising DRR solutions globally.</p>	<p>IP Owners: GNDR, UPV, and CMCC. Accessibility: Open/public within the GNDR network.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: Educational materials will remain available to GNDR members and relevant project partners beyond the end of the project. Disseminating tools and models through the GNDR Community Platform will enable members to adopt, adapt, and contextualize these resources within their local contexts. As the platform serves as GNDR's internal knowledge hub, it will continue to operate and facilitate exchange even after the project's completion.</p>
<p>KER 3.5 Educational materials on practises and strategies to react and adapt to urban pluvial floodings</p>		
<p>A comprehensive set of educational materials addressing urban pluvial flood management in Vilnius. The package includes information sheets for municipalities, lectures for architects and planners, and data-</p>	<p>IP Owner: VU Accessibility: Open/public educational resource.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: VU will maintain, update, and promote the materials across Lithuania, integrating them into academic modules (geography, climatology, hydrology) and</p>

<p>based case studies. The aim is to improve understanding of flood preparedness, adaptation strategies, and resilience practices among diverse audiences (decision-makers, practitioners, communities, and the public).</p>		<p>professional training. The outputs will raise stakeholder awareness and can be scaled to other cities or incorporated into custom education and research pro</p>
<p>KER3.6 - Educational material ("Fact sheet Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) curves in a climate change context")</p>		
<p>A methodological fact sheet explaining how to generate and apply IDF curves using historical and projected precipitation data (from LHMS and CMIP5/6 datasets). The material helps hydrometeorological services and planners integrate climate projections into storm-water design and urban risk assessment.</p>	<p>IP Owner: VU and CMCC Accessibility: Open/public educational resource.</p>	<p>Exploitation Strategy: The methodology will be shared with the National Hydrometeorological Service and local authorities to standardise the use of IDF curves in planning and adaptation measures. Future updates using CMIP6 data are foreseen. The fact sheet will be integrated into teaching materials and scientific dissemination activities, reinforcing its role in climate-change advocacy and education.</p>

5.2.4. Scientific Modelling, Monitoring, and Technological Innovation

This cluster groups together all the HuT Key results that push forward the scientific and technological frontiers of multi-hazard monitoring, modelling, and decision support.

These innovations form the analytical backbone of the HuT project, integrating real-time environmental data, multi-hazard simulation models, and exposure datasets to enable anticipatory risk management and evidence-based policymaking.

Table 6: Cluster 4- Scientific Modelling, Monitoring, and Technological Innovation.

<p>KER4.1 Innovative Nexus Monitoring</p>		
<p>The methodology introduces a cross-validation and integration of in-situ and remote sensing data to identify correlations and define new indicators for hydro-meteorological early warning systems. By combining heterogeneous datasets, the approach aims to enhance predictive accuracy beyond traditional rainfall thresholds,</p>	<p>Owner: UNISA, CMCC Accessibility: Open access</p>	<p>The exploitation strategy focuses on scientific dissemination through forthcoming publications, including a paper in <i>Earth Science Reviews</i> on Soil Water Content data integration, studies on correlations between rainfall, SWC, and hydrogeological events, and the</p>

<p>supporting a more comprehensive understanding of hydrogeological phenomena.</p>		<p>application of machine-learning algorithms for river discharge prediction. The methodology will be presented at 3FOMLINK (Florence) and is designed to be transferable and adaptable to other contexts and natural hazards, enabling replication and integration in multi-hazard monitoring systems. Future collaboration with regional and national authorities is envisaged to implement data-driven early warning frameworks.</p>
<p>KER4.2 Enhanced Monitoring Network (Val d’Aran)</p>		
<p>Upgrade of the environmental monitoring network in the Aran Valley to improve data coverage, accuracy, and reliability. The system integrates Type 1 and Type 2 LoRaWAN sensors measuring soil moisture, rainfall, temperature, and humidity. Type 1 sensors are co-located with existing stations for data correlation, while Type 2 sensors expand coverage to unmonitored areas. Data are collected hourly via a low-power IoT network, validated automatically, and visualised through dashboards and APIs for integration with the Early Warning System and forecasting models.</p>	<p>Owner: UPC / ARANTEC Accessibility: Data available through project database and API integration.</p>	<p>In the short term, the enhanced monitoring network will serve as a foundational system for future environmental monitoring projects in and beyond Val d’Aran. It demonstrates the reliability of LoRa technology for low-power, cost-effective data transmission in remote areas. The network can be replicated in other regions facing environmental risks and can support further research on sensor-based early warning systems. ARANTEC will consider offering the system as a commercial solution combining hardware (nodes, sensors, connectivity), software (data platform, forecast models), and maintenance services. The company can also provide integration and upgrades for existing monitoring networks.</p>
<p>KER4.3- Prototype of Early Warning System</p>		
<p>An automated platform comprising three main components: data collection, multi-hazard modelling, and warning emissions. The general framework will be developed in Python and hosted on an Amazon server. This tool aims to establish an initial</p>	<p>IP Owner: UPC ARANTEC Accessibility: Open Access, protected through copyright</p>	<p>The MH-EWS will be further tested and refined to reach full operational readiness (TRL 9) beyond the project. UPC and ARANTEC plan to upscale and replicate the system in other European regions exposed to</p>

<p>Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MH-EWS) to support decision-making related to flood and landslide risks in Val d'Aran. By the end of the project, the prototype of MH-EWS platform service for Val d'Aran will be delivered together with a transferable framework that other regions can directly adopt. Compared to other existing solutions is faster and addresses different hazards.</p>		<p>hydro-meteorological risks. In the short term, the tool will be demonstrated in Val d'Aran and offered to local authorities and emergency services as a decision-support platform for flood and landslide risk management. In the longer term, ARANTEC considers the commercial exploitation, offering the MH-EWS as a solution integrating sensors, data processing, and visualization services. UPC will contribute through scientific collaboration and model validation, ensuring adaptability of the system to new geographic contexts. Partnerships with public authorities and insurers will be sought to support replication, co-funding, and long-term maintenance.</p>
<p>KER4.4- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Software</p>		
<p>The Dynamic Exposure Modeling Software, developed by GFZ, calculates in real-time how people and buildings are exposed to multiple hazards, such as floods, earthquakes, and heatwaves, at a building-level resolution. It integrates and updates data from major sources including Google, Microsoft, and EUBUCCO, producing a dynamic representation of changing exposure patterns. The software operates as a collection of applications and libraries built on a PostGIS database and is fully available on GitLab as open source, with code reviews and extensive documentation.</p>	<p>IP Owner: GFZ Accessibility: open access in GitLab</p>	<p>GFZ plans to sustain and further develop the software through a dedicated non-profit organisation funded by industry partners. The system and datasets will remain publicly accessible under open or non-commercial licenses, while contributing partners will gain access to enhanced services through the NGO. This model ensures long-term maintenance, financial sustainability, and continued openness of the tool. The main target users include research institutions, civil protection authorities, urban planners, and the insurance sector.</p>
<p>KER4.5- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Service</p>		
<p>The Global Dynamic Exposure Model is available as an operational service through the GFZ Data Portal. It provides global, high-resolution</p>	<p>IP Owner: GFZ Accessibility: open access in GitLab</p>	<p>The service, maintained and distributed by GFZ, is offered in two modes: open access for research, humanitarian, and civil</p>

<p>exposure data that can be downloaded directly or accessed via an API. The service delivers continuously updated datasets describing population and building exposure to natural hazards, enabling applications such as evacuation planning, resource allocation, insurance risk pricing, urban planning, loss estimation, and reinsurance portfolio analysis.</p>		<p>protection use, and commercial access via annual subscriptions for professional users such as insurance and reinsurance companies. The strategy focuses on expanding adoption across research and risk management sectors while preserving its public-good mission. Sustainability will be ensured through partnerships and subscription revenues, supporting regular data updates and high computational performance.</p>
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KER4.6- Dynamic Exposure Modelling Data

<p>The Dynamic Exposure Modelling Data is a global, building-level PostGIS database providing detailed information on structure type, materials, height, occupancy, and population. Continuously updated using dynamic open data sources such as OpenStreetMap, it reflects real-world changes in near real time. The dataset supports accurate, time-sensitive analyses for disaster risk assessment, insurance modelling, and urban planning.</p>	<p>IP Owner: GFZ Accessibility: open access in GitLab</p>	<p>The dataset will be fully open; however, building-level information may raise privacy concerns, as it could contain personal or sensitive data. In such cases, specific access agreements will be required. Aggregated or anonymised versions will remain openly accessible. The Global Dynamic Exposure Model Group at GFZ will maintain and update the dataset. For commercial use, access will be based on an annual subscription model, while research and humanitarian users will continue to have free access.</p>
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KER4.7- Methodology for the development of fire-prevention strategies

<p>This result delivers a transferable methodology that combines scientific and local knowledge to design sustainable and adaptable fire-prevention strategies. The framework integrates simulation tools and participatory processes, supporting decision-making and stakeholder engagement for effective land and fire management. Its flexible structure allows application in diverse regional</p>	<p>Owner: CNR and Confagricoltura Accessibility: Open/public through reports, presentations, and training materials.</p>	<p>The methodology will be primarily exploited for research and scientific advancement, with potential replication in other territories through collaboration with local and regional administrations. Successful uptake relies on strong stakeholder participation and institutional commitment. Future exploitation may occur through</p>
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<p>contexts, enhancing territorial resilience to climate-driven fire risks.</p>		<p>training, consultancy, and integration into regional land management and fire-prevention plans.</p>
<p>KER4.8- Knowledge Advancements in Designing Fire Prevention Options</p>		
<p>This result advances scientific understanding of how to integrate local and scientific knowledge in the design of fire-prevention solutions under current and future climate conditions. It contributes to developing more effective and sustainable prevention measures by adapting them to the specific environmental and socio-economic characteristics of each region.</p>	<p>Owner: CNR and CMCC Accessibility: Open/public through scientific publications and dissemination materials.</p>	<p>Scientific exploitation through peer-reviewed publications and conferences. The knowledge generated supports future methodological development (KER 8.1b) and can inform regional and national fire-prevention strategies, contributing to evidence-based policy and planning in fire-prone areas.</p>
<p>KER4.9- Review of the Criteria for Heatwave Definition and Analysis of Past Heatwaves in the Valencia Region</p>		
<p>This result provides a scientific review and analysis of past and future heatwaves in the city of Valencia using bias-adjusted CMIP6 climate models under different scenarios. It evaluates model suitability and applies operational definitions of heatwaves to identify temperature thresholds relevant for local adaptation planning. The study supports improved understanding of heatwave dynamics in the Mediterranean context.</p>	<p>Owner: UPV Protection: Copyright Accessibility: Open/public through scientific publication (<i>Urban Climate Journal</i>).</p>	<p>Scientific exploitation through peer-reviewed publication and research dissemination. UPV and collaborating researchers will maintain and update the methodology post-project to ensure continued use and adaptation for further studies on heatwave monitoring and climate risk assessment.</p>
<p>KER4.10- Methodology for the Analysis of Heatwaves and Urban Heat Island Effects</p>		
<p>This result develops a climate and spatial analysis methodology to model the distribution of heat within the urban fabric of Valencia, identify vulnerable populations, and design mitigation strategies. It integrates CMIP6 model outputs across multiple scenarios to produce actionable data at the neighborhood scale, supporting urban adaptation and planning.</p>	<p>Owner: UPV Protection: Copyright Accessibility: Open/public; results published in scientific outlets.</p>	<p>The model can be replicated and adapted for other cities in the Valencian region or in similar Mediterranean urban environments. UPV and regional authorities will maintain and update the methodology beyond the project to ensure its continuous applicability and openness for research and policy use.</p>

5.2.5. Operational and Policy Protocols for Multi-Risk Management

Table 7: Cluster 5- Operational and Policy Protocols for Multi-Risk Management.

KER5.1- Protocols for Early Warning System (EWS) Application		
<p>This KER introduces a replicable methodology and digital tool supporting the design and operation of landslide early warning systems based on real-time data. Developed by NGI, the protocol integrates soil moisture and pore pressure sensors, automated email/SMS alerts, and data-driven thresholds. The methodology has undergone technical validation and is provided as open-source Python code available on GitHub. It can be directly implemented by local authorities or system managers without the need for external facilitation.</p>	<p>IP Owner: NGI Accessibility: Open access (Python codes available on GitHub); NGI may offer training and certification services for operational use.</p>	<p>The protocol will be exploited through scientific dissemination, replication in other DEM sites, and integration in future DRR and EWS projects. Promotion will occur via publications, workshops, and technical conferences, with potential alignment to EU Civil Protection and national early warning guidelines. NGI is considering offering consultancy and training services for system customization and maintenance, leveraging its expertise to support adoption by public authorities and private operators.</p>
KER5.2- Policy Recommendations and Briefs on Inclusive Risk Communication		
<p>Policy brief produced by GNDR to guide policymakers in communicating early warnings in more inclusive and actionable ways. The brief highlights key principles of public engagement and inclusiveness, identifying success factors for community-centred communication. It targets local, national, and international stakeholders involved in DRR and early warning, providing practical guidance to improve accessibility, clarity, and trust in warning messages. The brief is disseminated through GNDR's community platform, global networks, and major policy forums.</p>	<p>IP Owner: GNDR Accessibility: publicly available on GNDR's community platform</p>	<p>The brief will be advocated through GNDR's global network of over 2,000 members, leveraging partnerships with UNDRR, REAP, and local authorities to ensure uptake. It aims to influence policies and practices on early warning and early action within national DRR strategies and international frameworks such as the Sendai Framework. GNDR will maintain and regularly update these policy recommendations beyond the project, embedding them into ongoing advocacy and capacity-building initiatives.</p>

5.2.6. Financial Instruments for Climate and Risk Management

This cluster focuses on innovative approaches to risk financing and insurance within the broader framework of integrated disaster risk management. Four key results have been mapped under this area, all aiming to strengthen the role of financial instruments in supporting prevention, preparedness, and recovery through the integration of climate and hazard intelligence.

The activities include the development of conceptual frameworks and prototype tools for climate-informed insurance products, as well as analytical work on existing risk transfer and financing mechanisms. Collectively, these results enhance the interface between scientific knowledge, policy frameworks, and market practices, contributing to the creation of more resilient and adaptive financial systems capable of addressing climate-related risks.

Given that this deliverable (D6.5) is publicly available, specific technical and commercial details are not disclosed in this section.

6. Dissemination & Communication

6.1. KERs, Stakeholders and Dissemination Formats

To determine the most appropriate dissemination formats for each Key Exploitable Result (KER), The HuT consortium adopted a stakeholder-driven approach, grounded in the insights gathered from the exploitation strategies and stakeholder presented in the previous sections.

For each KER cluster identified in the previous chapter, the core stakeholder groups were identified according to their relevance to the expected use and uptake of project results ranging from local and regional authorities, civil protection agencies, and policymakers to researchers, SMEs, educators, and civil-society actors. The analysis of these groups and their roles, together with the specific exploitation pathways designed for each KER, guided the definition of tailored dissemination formats.

This approach ensures that every stakeholder group receives content through the most suitable and accessible format, whether technical, educational, or policy-oriented, thereby enhancing the visibility, understanding, and adoption potential of The HuT results at local, national, and international levels.

The tables below represent the KERs, Stakeholders, and dedicated dissemination formats for each cluster identified in the previous chapter.

Cluster 1 – Local and International DRR Nexus Forums

Table 8: Cluster 1 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 1.1 Local DRR Nexus Forum – Amalfi	Municipality of Amalfi; Civil Protection; local utilities; NGOs; academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Factsheet • Workshop • Short Video • Scientific Publications
KER 1.2 Local DRR Nexus Forum – Vilnius	Municipality departments; utilities; insurers; civil protection; academia; NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Factsheet • Workshop • Short Video • Scientific Publication
KER 1.3 Local DRR Nexus Forum – Bern Canton	Forest managers; NGOs; cantonal authorities; hazard experts; private stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Factsheet • Workshop
KER 1.4 International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF)	Researchers; practitioners; policymakers; Demonstration Site representatives; external experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Factsheet • Workshop

Cluster 2 – Local Data Portals

Table 9: Cluster 2 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 2.1 Local Data Portal – Amalfi	Municipality of Amalfi; Civil Protection; UNISA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Short Video
KER 2.2 Database of Pluvial Flood Events – Vilnius	Vilnius University (VU); Municipality of Vilnius; public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publication • Workshop
Sub-KER 2.2a Database of Precipitation (IDF Curves) – Vilnius	CMCC; Vilnius University (VU); urban-planning authorities; civil engineers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Training materials • Workshop • Scientific publication
Sub-KER 2.2b Analysis of Precipitation Impact – Vilnius	CMCC; Vilnius University (VU); municipal decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Scientific publication
KER 2.3 Local Data Portal – Canton of Bern	Meteo GmbH; UNIGE; Canton of Bern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Policy brief
KER 2.4 Local Data Portal – Val d’Aran	UPC; ARANTEC; local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Short Video

Cluster 3 – Education and Capacity Building

Table 10: Cluster 3 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 3.1 Multihazard DRR Academy	UNISA; early-career researchers; practitioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Training materials • Workshop • Scientific Publication
KER 3.2 Educational Materials for High School Pupils	UNISA; schools in Campania Region; teachers; public institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials
KER 3.3 Serious Games for Cascading and Compound Impacts	UNISA; CMCC; GFZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Short Video
KER 3.4 Educational Materials on DRR Solutions (GNDR Platform)	GNDR; UPV; CMCC; GNDR community members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials • Workshop • Short Video

KER 3.5 Educational Materials on Urban Pluvial Flooding (Vilnius)	Vilnius University (VU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials • Workshop • Scientific Publications
KER 3.6 Fact Sheet on IDF Curves in a Climate Change Context	Vilnius University (VU); CMCC; National Hydrometeorological Service; local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials • Workshop • Short Video • Factsheet

Cluster 4 – Scientific Modelling, Monitoring and Technological Innovation

Table 11: Cluster 4 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 4.1 Innovative Nexus Monitoring	UNISA; CMCC; regional and national authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Short Video
KER 4.2 Enhanced Monitoring Network (Val d’Aran)	UPC; ARANTEC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Short Video
KER 4.3 Prototype of Early Warning System (MH-EWS)	UPC; ARANTEC; local authorities; emergency services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop
KER 4.4 Dynamic Exposure Modelling Software	GFZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Factsheet
KER 4.5 Dynamic Exposure Modelling Service	GFZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Factsheet
KER 4.6 Dynamic Exposure Modelling Data	GFZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Factsheet
KER 4.7 Methodology for Fire-Prevention Strategies	CNR; Confagricoltura	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Factsheet
KER 4.8 Knowledge Advancements in Designing Fire-Prevention Options	CNR; CMCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Workshop • Factsheet
KER 4.9 Review of Heatwave Definition and Analysis (Valencia)	UPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Factsheet
KER 4.10 Methodology for Analysis of Heatwaves and Urban Heat Islands	UPV; regional authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Factsheet

Cluster 5 – Operational and Policy Protocols for Multi-Risk Management

Table 12: Cluster 5 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 5.1 Protocols for Early Warning System Application	NGI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheet • Policy Brief
KER 5.2 Policy Recommendations on Inclusive Risk Communication	GNDR; policymakers; REAP; UNDRR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Brief

Cluster 6 – Financial Instruments for Climate and Risk Management

Table 13: Cluster 6 Dissemination Formats.

KER	Key Stakeholders	Dissemination formats
KER 6.x Climate-Informed Insurance and Risk-Transfer Tools	Not disclosed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials • Factsheets

6.2. Dissemination & Communication Channels

6.2.1. Monitoring Methodology

In the following chapters and sections, we will analyze the impact generated by The HuT's communication channels, editorial formats, and social media platforms.

The initial methodology and monitoring framework were defined in *Deliverable D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results*, and have been progressively refined and implemented during the project's lifetime to ensure consistent performance tracking and evidence-based evaluation.

The monitoring methodology applied in The HuT relies on outreach and engagement indicators, derived from data collected through dedicated web analytics and monitoring tools.

- **Outreach indicators** measure both online and offline communication reach, estimating the number of people exposed to project content. They provide insight into overall visibility and the project's impact on public awareness.
- **Engagement indicators**, on the other hand, evaluate the level of interaction generated by project activities and materials, revealing stakeholder interest and the degree of audience involvement.

Before delving into the individual metrics, it is important to note that all communication and dissemination activities collectively contribute to the **Community Engagement Index (CEI)**, a comprehensive indicator of the project's overall impact in terms of C&D performance. The CEI

expresses the **ratio between total outreach and total engagement**, providing an integrated measure of the cumulative impact achieved through all activities.

The Community Engagement Index (CEI) comprises three complementary dimensions:

- **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)**: measures interaction with project publications and editorial outputs.
- **Social Engagement Index (SEI)**: evaluates visibility and engagement on social media platforms.
- **Website Engagement Index (WEI)**: analyses user behavior and interaction on the project website.

For The HuT, the CEI reaches a score of 70, reflecting a strong balance between outreach and engagement, with 162,588 total outreach and 23,914 engagement interactions.

The benchmark of ICONS projects working in Climate & Environment shows an average CEI of 56. Within this group, The HuT performs strongly, above the sector average. This confirms that The HuT is one of the best-performing climate & environment projects, combining visibility with high engagement.

This result demonstrates the project's effective use of integrated communication formats and channels in fostering awareness, visibility, and active participation within its community.

6.2.2. Website

As already described in Deliverable D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, The HuT website serves as the central communication hub for all project updates, resources, and events. It ensures transparent and accessible dissemination of information to a wide range of stakeholders — from local authorities and researchers to citizens and policymakers.

The website's user-friendly design enables intuitive navigation across key sections, including About the Project, Demonstration Sites, News and Events, and Resources. These sections collectively communicate The HuT's objectives, progress, and outputs, supporting visibility and stakeholder engagement throughout the project's lifecycle.

In addition, the Resources section provides access to downloadable materials such as factsheets, newsletters, and policy briefs, while the News area highlights dissemination activities, publications, and project participation in external events from each Demonstrator, in the local language if need be. This structure ensures that both scientific and non-technical audiences can easily locate relevant content and follow the project's evolution.

Since its launch, The HuT website has recorded a total **outreach of 37,708** and **engagement of 16,161**, reflecting the project's growing visibility and strong interaction with its target audiences.

Figure 4 represents an analysis of user behavior shows that **40% of visitors spend less than 10 seconds** on the website, indicating that a significant share of users accesses the site for quick information — such as checking event announcements, partner links, or contact details. However, **over half of the audience (60%) stays longer than 10 seconds**, demonstrating sustained interest in the project's content.

In particular, **14% of users spend between 1 and 3 minutes**, and an additional **24 % remain for more than 3 minutes** (181–1800 seconds), suggesting that these visitors are engaging more deeply with technical materials, publications, and demonstrator content. This balance between short exploratory visits and long reading sessions confirms that the website effectively serves both casual visitors seeking quick insights and professionals looking for in-depth resources.

Figure 4: Time spent by the users.

Figure 5: WEI.

The **Website Engagement Index (WEI)** is used to measure user interest in the website over time.

This composite indicator combines two main dimensions: **outreach**, measured by the number of page views, and **engagement**, reflecting the level of user interaction with the site. Engagement is evaluated through metrics such as **time spent on the website, pages viewed per session, number of clicks, and user actions** (e.g. downloads of materials or access to external links).

In the current reporting period, the HuT website reached an **outreach of 37,708** and an **engagement of 16,161**, corresponding to a **WEI of 78**. This score confirms a steady and positive trend in online visibility and interaction, illustrating that visitors not only access the website but also actively explore its content, particularly the demonstration site pages, news articles, and downloadable resources.

The figure below represents the homepage (**12,022 page views; 9,518 unique views**) and *Project* section (**2,569 page views**) remain the most visited areas, confirming users' interest in understanding the project's overall objectives and scope. High engagement is also recorded in sections such as *Territories* (**1,272 views**) and *Partners Area* (**706 views**), demonstrating that visitors actively explore the Demonstration Sites and consortium activities.

Content-driven pages, such as news articles (e.g., "When theatre tackles the effects of climate extremes" – **412 views**) and territory-specific sections (Valencia, East Fjords, Bern Canton, Val d'Aran, Lattari Mountains), show that users engage deeply with storytelling and local impact narratives. The *Resources* and *News* sections further support sustained interaction, with **695** and **629** views respectively, highlighting interest in project materials, publications, and event updates.

The dissemination and communication strategy continues to focus on **strengthening both outreach and engagement**, particularly by leveraging the website as a gateway to HuT’s demonstrator stories, digital tools, and educational content. The upcoming inclusion of final project outputs such as the “HuT for Me and You” climate stories — will further enhance traceability, accessibility, and knowledge sharing across audiences ranging from civil protection agencies to citizens.

URL	Page views	Unique Page views
https://thehut-nexus.eu/	12,022	9,518
https://thehut-nexus.eu/project/	2,569	2,019
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territories/	1,272	1,030
https://thehut-nexus.eu/partners-area/	706	621
https://thehut-nexus.eu/resources/	695	565
https://thehut-nexus.eu/news/	629	489
https://thehut-nexus.eu/events/	544	424
https://thehut-nexus.eu/contacts/	427	383
https://thehut-nexus.eu/when-theatre-tackles-the-effects-of-climate-extremes-the-science-art-approach-to-disaster-risk-reduction/	412	339
https://thehut-nexus.eu/subscribe/	269	241
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/east-fjords/	197	157
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/valencia/	188	159
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/lattari-mountains/	180	154
https://thehut-nexus.eu/from-victims-to-ambassadors-of-change-how-children-can-educate-communities-on-disaster-risk-reduction/	179	141
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/berne-canton/	176	148
https://thehut-nexus.eu/privacy-notice/	160	133
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/schleswig-holstein-state/	159	133
https://thehut-nexus.eu/resource_category/deliverable/	150	121
https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/val-daran-region/	149	126
https://thehut-nexus.eu/theatre-performance-storie-in-piena-at-teatro-di-san-rocco/	149	121

Figure 6: Page views for each section on The Hut website.

6.2.3. Social Media Networks

The HuT’s social media channels, LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter), were launched in M3 to ensure continuous visibility and engagement across key audiences, including researchers, policymakers, civil protection actors, and citizens. As of Month 37, the project’s online presence has grown steadily, supported by a consistent and coordinated communication strategy.

Across both channels, The HuT has published 522 posts, achieving an outreach of 83,000 and an engagement of 11,000, with 2,773 video views generated through the project’s multimedia campaigns. The community currently counts 845 followers, distributed primarily between LinkedIn (555) and X/Twitter (260), with a smaller but active presence on Facebook (30).

The project's Social Engagement Index (SEI) a composite indicator combining the number of followers, interactions, and post reach currently stands at 52, reflecting a balanced and growing level of visibility and interaction within the European research and innovation community.

Figure 7: Trends by channels and engagement and outreach.

The evolution of The HuT's social media channels demonstrates **steady audience growth and consistent engagement** since their launch in Month 3. The **trend in followers** indicates a continuous upward trajectory across both LinkedIn and X/Twitter, with notable acceleration from **Month 18 onwards**, coinciding with the dissemination of demonstrator updates and project event coverage. LinkedIn remains the most influential channel, showing a sustained increase in followers month by month, while X/Twitter maintains a stable base and serves as a complementary platform for real-time communication and event promotion.

The **activity and engagement trends** confirm a solid alignment between posting frequency and user interaction. Periods of higher outreach (notably between **May and August 2023**) correspond to targeted campaigns, participation in EU events, and collaborative posts with sister projects. Engagement remains consistent over time, demonstrating that audiences respond positively to visual storytelling, short videos, and news linked to the Demonstration Sites.

6.2.4. Social Media Campaigns

To maximise online visibility and engagement, The HuT has implemented a series of **targeted social media campaigns** designed to highlight key milestones, foster stakeholder participation, and disseminate project results in accessible and impactful ways. Each campaign was planned around strategic project events or international awareness days, aligning communication efforts with the broader objectives of the project's dissemination and exploitation strategy.

Key campaigns carried out during the reporting period include:

- **Promotion of Demonstration Site activities** – featuring posts, videos, and interviews from partners in Valencia, Bern, Vilnius, Amalfi, and Val d'Aran, strengthening connections with local stakeholders and communities.
- **Sister-project collaborations within the Societal Resilience Cluster (SRC)** – joint announcements and shared posts with projects such as KNOWING, NEVERMORE, and PARATUS to enhance cross-visibility and policy outreach.
- **International Day for Disaster Risk Reduction (13 October 2024, 2025)** – a coordinated campaign across all platforms celebrating the UN day and showcasing The HuT's contribution to advancing disaster-risk-reduction knowledge and practice. This campaign

recorded one of the highest interaction peaks of the period, confirming audience interest in global DRR themes.

These campaigns proved instrumental in **driving engagement** and strengthening The HuT's online identity.

6.2.5. Newsletters

Since its launch, The HuT has published three newsletters, serving as a key dissemination tool to update stakeholders on project progress, events, and results. The newsletters are distributed via direct mailing and promoted through the project's website and social media channels, ensuring broad visibility and accessibility across target audiences.

The first issue was released on 14 March 2024, followed by the second in November 2024 and the third in September 2025. Together, these editions have contributed to maintaining consistent engagement throughout the project's implementation, highlighting milestones such as the Demonstration Site activities, climate stories, and collaborative initiatives within the Societal Resilience Cluster.

The project's mailing list currently counts 217 subscribers, representing a diverse mix of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, practitioners, civil protection authorities, and citizens interested in disaster risk reduction and climate resilience. This growing subscriber base reflects the effectiveness of The HuT's outreach efforts and the relevance of its communication content.

For future newsletters, it is recommended to maintain a balance between continuity and novelty, building on previous content while introducing fresh insights or interactive elements to sustain reader engagement. ICONS will support project partners in producing engaging content aligned with key project milestones. This approach will help attract a broader audience and enable the promotion of the newsletter in a more structured and strategic way.

6.3. Dissemination & Communication materials and formats

6.3.1. Communication Kit & Project Video

Communication Kit

The HuT **Communication Kit** was launched in **May 2023 (Month 8)** to provide partners with a coherent set of visual and promotional materials that ensure consistent communication and branding across all dissemination activities.

The kit includes the project's **visual identity, flyer, roll-up banner, PowerPoint template, and presentation video**, all designed to reflect The HuT's integrated approach to disaster risk reduction and climate resilience. The materials were created in alignment with the project's graphic guidelines to guarantee visual consistency and recognizability across online and offline communication tools.

The Communication Kit supports partners in promoting the project at workshops, conferences, exhibitions, and external events, while also serving as a key resource for digital outreach. All materials are made **available for download** on the project website, ensuring accessibility for both consortium members and external audiences.

Project Video

The HuT project video was produced in M6 and serves as a key communication asset introducing the project's concept, objectives, and expected impacts. The video is publicly available on the project's website and official YouTube channel(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ib7i-f4DDhs>), ensuring accessibility for a broad audience of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, civil protection authorities, and citizens.

Since its release, the video has generated 364 views, contributing to the overall visibility and outreach of The HuT's online communication strategy. It is regularly featured in social media posts, newsletters, and event presentations, supporting the promotion of the project's activities and Demonstration Sites.

6.3.2. Scientific Publications

With the support of ICONS, The HuT's technical and scientific partners are producing a series of scientific articles and papers to be published in peer-reviewed journals and international conference proceedings. These publications will showcase the project's cutting-edge research results, methodologies, and technological innovations developed across the Demonstration Sites.

The scientific outputs will address themes such as multi-hazard monitoring, dynamic exposure modelling, fire-prevention methodologies, and heatwave and urban heat-island analyses, among others. Each paper will contribute to advancing the scientific understanding of integrated disaster risk reduction management, climate adaptation, and resilience planning.

By ensuring open-access publication whenever possible, The HuT aims to maximise the visibility, accessibility, and impact of its research findings within the European and international scientific community.

6.3.3. Factsheets

In collaboration with MET and ICONS, The HuT has produced two fact sheets presenting key insights and results from the project. The factsheets are available for download in the Resources section of the project website

- [First Factsheet for The Hut \(September 2024\) - Designing early warning services](#)
- [Second Factsheet \(June 2025\) - From Sensors to Safety: The HuT Explores IoT's Role in Predicting Natural Hazards](#)

6.3.4. Editorial contents

The HuT project has successfully increased visibility, fostered stakeholder engagement, and broadened its audience by disseminating diverse online content across multiple channels.

From the start, editorial production has followed a regular and strategic schedule, ensuring a continuous flow of high-quality publications aligned with the project's milestones and events. In total, 61 editorial products have been published and are available on the project website.

According to the ICONS monitoring methodology, the Publication Engagement Index (PEI) measures the impact of both written and audiovisual content by calculating the ratio between engagement and outreach. To date, The HuT's editorial outputs have reached 90K users and generated 5,618 interactions, resulting in a PEI score of 33, which demonstrates the project's strong capacity to attract and retain audience attention through its published materials.

The following **editorial formats** have been produced throughout The HuT project implementation period:

- **2 journalistic articles** written by ICONS' professional journalists, focusing on trending topics intersecting with the project's research areas.
- **7 event releases** highlighting The HuT's participation in national and international occasions.
- **24 project updates** providing short news about progress and key developments from the project.
- **18 news releases** have been produced.
- **3 newsletters** offering periodic updates to keep subscribers informed about recent highlights, achievements, and upcoming events.
- **1 press release** distributed to media outlets to announce key results and milestones.
- **1 presentation video** introducing the project's concept and objectives to a broad audience.
- **4 video interviews** featuring project partners and experts sharing insights on The HuT's work, results, and impact.

Figure 8: Effectiveness quadrants by publication type.

An analysis of The HuT's effectiveness quadrants by publication type highlights the strong performance of video interviews and social media clips, which achieved the highest average engagement levels among all content formats. These dynamic, visual materials effectively captured audience attention, confirming the importance of storytelling and partner-led communication in driving interaction.

In contrast, project updates and news releases — while generating higher outreach — registered more moderate engagement rates, indicating their key role in maintaining visibility and informing audiences about progress rather than triggering active interaction. Event releases and press releases performed consistently, supporting visibility during milestones and external events, while articles and newsletters provided valuable depth for recurring audiences.

Overall, the data demonstrate that The HuT’s communication mix is well balanced, combining high-reach informational content with high-engagement audiovisual formats. This approach ensures both broad dissemination and meaningful stakeholder interaction, contributing to the project’s strong online performance and an effective Publication Engagement Index (PEI).

Looking ahead, future editorial efforts will continue to prioritise audiovisual storytelling, partner-driven interviews, and short video formats to sustain engagement growth, while maintaining a steady flow of informative updates and news releases to reinforce visibility and scientific credibility.

Press and news, event releases, and project updates

When filtering The HuT’s editorial outputs by performance, the top-performing format in terms of outreach is the news release, reaching over 16,600 users, followed by project updates (around 10,000) and event releases (approximately 3,000).

In terms of engagement, project updates lead with more than 1,100 interactions, followed by news releases (about 1,000) and event releases (around 180). The average Publication Engagement Index (PEI) confirms this trend: project updates achieve the highest rate (66), demonstrating their ability to maintain consistent interaction through partner-driven storytelling and real-time project highlights.

Table 14: Total Outreach and Total Engagement.

Type	Total outreach	Total engagement	Average PEI
Press Release	2,024	107	28
News Release	16,637	1,016	41
Project Update	10,070	1,192	66
Event Release	3,041	178	40
Total	26,865	2,227	44

Video interviews

The first round of The HuT video interviews has been successfully conducted, featuring project partners and stakeholders sharing insights on their activities, achievements, and perspectives within the Demonstration Sites. These interviews contribute to enhancing the project’s visibility and storytelling by translating technical outcomes into accessible narratives for broader audiences.

Table 15 represents the Outreach and Engagement generated by the Video Interviews, achieving a total **outreach of 3,397** and **engagement of 1,071**. These interviews, released under the series “Early Warnings, Big Challenges, and the Future of DRR – #BehindTheHuT,” provided valuable expert perspectives on disaster risk reduction, climate adaptation, and early warning systems. Their positive reception demonstrates the strong interest of the audience in expert-led storytelling and the relevance of The HuT’s research themes to the broader disaster resilience community.

A **second round of interview** releases is planned for **December 2025**, in collaboration with **MET**, to capture the lessons learned, and perspectives for post-project exploitation and sustainability.

The new interviews will complement the first series, ensuring comprehensive coverage of *The HuT's* progress and impact throughout its implementation.

All interviews are disseminated through the project's website, social media channels, and newsletters, reinforcing engagement with both technical experts and the general public.

Table 15: Video Interviews outreach and engagement.

Title	Outreach	Engagement
Brian Golding: Early Warnings, Big Challenges, and the Future of DRR – #BehindTheHuT	1,158	390
Guido Rianna: Early Warnings, Big Challenges, and the Future of DRR – #BehindTheHuT	1,004	219
Harpa Grímsdóttir: Early Warnings, Big Challenges, and the Future of DRR – #BehindTheHuT	510	212
Marcel Hürlimann: Early Warnings, Big Challenges, and the Future of DRR – #BehindTheHuT	725	250
Total	3, 397	1,071

Journalistic Article

The HuT has published two journalistic articles, written by ICONS' professional journalists, focusing on the intersection of science, society, and creative engagement in disaster risk reduction (DRR).

- [“When theatre tackles the effects of climate extremes: the ‘science-art’ approach to disaster risk reduction” \(February 27, 2024\)](#): explores how artistic and performative practices can complement scientific communication, fostering public understanding and emotional connection to climate challenges.
- [“From victims to ambassadors of change: How children can educate communities on disaster risk reduction” \(August 4, 2025\)](#): highlights the role of education and storytelling in empowering younger generations to promote resilience and awareness within their communities.

Both articles were widely disseminated through The HuT website and social media channels, and media multipliers reinforcing the project's commitment to accessible, narrative-driven communication and bridging the gap between research, culture, and civil society.

N	Date	Title	Type	Auth or	Thematic Area	Outreach	Engagement	PEI
22	2/26/2024	When theatre tackles the effects of climate extremes: the "science-art" approach to disaster risk reduction	Article	Diego Giulia ni		51,413	1,141	12
58	8/4/2025	From victims to ambassadors of change. How children can educate communities on disaster risk reduction	Article			5,055	215	22
Total						56,468	1,356	13

Figure 9: Articles outreach and engagement.

6.4. Networking activities

The consortium has actively strengthened its connections with internationally recognized networks and European research initiatives addressing complementary themes relevant to The HuT.

These collaborations aim to:

- Broaden the project's collaborative reach, fostering synergies that extend beyond the consortium's initial boundaries; and
- Ensure the long-term legacy and scalability of The HuT's innovations through sustained knowledge exchange and joint visibility.

To this end, The HuT has engaged with several Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, including **CORE, MYRIAD-EU, C2IMPRESS, DISTENDER, DIRECTED, RESILIAGE, PARATUS, and PEERS**. In addition to the projects mentioned before, The HuT is also currently in contact with **Firelogue** and **NATURANCE** projects.

Such interactions facilitate cross-project learning, mutual dissemination, and coordinated participation in cluster activities and events.

Moreover, The HuT is an active member of the Societal Resilience Cluster of Projects, within the **Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe (CMINE) a group endorsed by both CERIS and the Research Executive Agency (REA)**. Through this cluster, the project contributes to joint webinars, workshops, and communication initiatives that collectively promote innovation in disaster risk reduction and crisis management.

These continuous networking efforts are consolidating The HuT's position within the European resilience research ecosystem and ensuring that its methodologies, lessons learned, and tools will remain accessible and relevant beyond the project's duration.

7. Conclusions

The HuT CDE strategy has progressively evolved from visibility and stakeholder engagement (D6.1 & D6.2) toward a more impact-oriented approach, where communication, dissemination and exploitation reinforce each other. In this updated plan (D6.5), the focus shifts from what we produce to how the project's results can be adopted, replicated, and sustained beyond the project lifecycle.

From an **exploitation standpoint**, three major achievements stand out:

- **Mapping, clustering, and prioritisation of 24 KERs and sub-KERs**, involving all partners and Demonstration Sites.
- **Clear identification of owners, TRLs, accessibility formats, and potential users** for each result.
- **Preliminary exploitation strategies** defined for each KER, ranging across scientific exploitation, operational uptake by public authorities, commercial services, open-source software, policy recommendations, and training formats.

This version of the CDE plan confirms that The HuT outputs do not stand alone but form an integrated ecosystem that connects:

- Local governance (Local DRR Nexus Forums)
- Data and infrastructure (Local Data Portals & Monitoring Networks)
- Operational tools (Early Warning Systems, Dynamic Exposure, climate models)
- Financial mechanisms (insurance prototypes, risk financing concepts)
- Education & Capacity Building (Academy, educational toolkits, serious games)

To move from preliminary strategies to actual exploitation, the following actions will be prioritised in the final project phase and reported in the Final Exploitation Plan (D6.4):

- Finalisation of KER exploitation roadmaps and business and governance models
- Completion of IPR strategies and licensing agreements (open-source, copyright, commercial licences)
- Replication plans for KERs across other regions/projects
- Funding pathways for post-project sustainability.

From the **Communication and Dissemination** standpoint, The HuT will continue to build on the solid foundations established during the first three years of the project. In the final phase, the consortium will focus on producing **targeted formats** that strengthen the visibility and uptake of results among key audiences, ensuring that communication activities directly support the project's exploitation pathways.

The HuT will also continue to **expand its networking activities** across EU and international initiatives, enhancing its position within the resilience and disaster risk reduction community. Particular attention will be devoted to **growing the project's editorial presence**, increasing the number and quality of **scientific and journalistic publications**, and consequently raising the **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)**.

The next months will see the launch of “The HuT for Me and You” narrative, which is a storytelling initiative designed to translate scientific and technical outcomes into relatable, human-centered stories. In parallel, the consortium will strengthen its **social media strategy**, producing more **audiovisual content and short videos** to amplify outreach and maintain active engagement with the project’s online community.

Overall, the CDE strategy will remain dynamic and adaptive, ensuring that The HuT continues to inform, inspire, and connect stakeholders.

